

Supplementary Material

Supplementary Figure S1: Breakdown of sequencing reads for each of the 51 shotgun metagenomics samples. Bars represent, for each sample, the number of reads removed during quality filtering (red), reads mapped to the human genome and excluded from analysis (yellow), reads that could not be taxonomically classified to microbial species by AGAMEMNON (green), and reads that were successfully classified to microbial species (blue). The bottom 17 samples correspond to gingival crevicular fluid, the middle 17 to subgingival plaque, and the top 17 to supragingival plaque.